

Cooling Systems: Fluid flow in engine cooling systems and Advanced cooling technologies for electric vehicles.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Thermal management technology is a core key technology for both internal combustion engine (ICE) and pure electric vehicle (BEV) powertrain systems, directly affecting the operational efficiency and service life of the core components of the vehicle's power system. In vehicles dominated by internal combustion engines, the traditional cooling system has technical flaws in fluid transportation, such as excessively high local thermal stress, significant pressure drop loss, and uneven distribution of the cooling fluid flow field, which largely affect the optimization and improvement of the overall performance of the internal combustion engine.

1.2. Current situation of the problem

With global automotive electrification, high-rate fast charging and high-power-density electric drives have brought unprecedented thermal management challenges for BEVs. Unlike ICE cooling systems, BEV thermal management must simultaneously handle heat dissipation of drive components and maintain lithium-ion batteries within a narrow optimal temperature range. Heat accumulation and temperature inconsistency during fast charging will accelerate battery degradation and even trigger thermal runaway, becoming a key technical bottleneck for BEV development.

1.3. Research Objective

This paper systematically analyzes the fluid flow characteristics and their impacts on cooling performance in ICE cooling systems, and conducts a comparative study of advanced BEV cooling technologies from mainstream solutions to cutting-edge intelligent strategies. The findings are expected to provide reference for the optimal design of high-performance automotive thermal management systems.

2. Fluid Flow in Engine Cooling Systems

2.1 Flow Patterns

2.1.1 Forced Convection Circulation (Water Pump Driven)

This method differs from natural convection in some respects. Natural convection mainly relies on the effect of thermal buoyancy. However, the first approach adopted was another method, which was the use of a mechanical pump. This pump could generate a pressure difference and then drive the coolant to circulate throughout the system to achieve the cooling circuit. The pump pressurizes the coolant flowing out from the radiator, causing it to pass through the engine block, cylinder head, and auxiliary components in sequence, and finally return to the radiator for heat dissipation.^[1] Its effect is that this mechanism can effectively eliminate the risks caused by fluid stagnation after low-temperature conditions. Even when the engine is running slowly, it can ensure that the flow rate of the coolant is not too low, thereby guaranteeing the basic cooling capacity.

2.1.2 Steady and Transient Flow

A stable flow refers to the flow state where the flow parameters (such as flow velocity, pressure, and flow rate) remain constant. It maintains a constant state at a specific point over time. In contrast, a transient flow describes the dynamic response of the flow parameters to changes. In a stable engine operating condition (such as constant-speed cruise), the coolant flow is in a stable state. During transient processes, such as acceleration, cold start, or load

switching, the pump speed and valve positions are adjusted rapidly to cause dynamic changes in flow and wave propagation in the flow path.^[2] The transient flow regulation function enables the cooling system to adapt to real-time thermal load variations, thereby preventing overheating when the load increases and avoiding undercooling when operating at low loads, optimizing the thermal response speed of the engine.

2.1.3 Laminar and Turbulent Flow

These two flow states can be distinguished by the Reynolds number (Re): when the Reynolds number is lower than 2300, a laminar flow phenomenon occurs, where the fluid flows in an orderly layered manner; while at high Reynolds numbers greater than 4000, turbulent flow occurs, and the fluid moves in a chaotic and disorderly state, accompanied by vortex phenomena. In the engine cooling system, the laminar flow state may occur under low flow conditions, while in most normal operating conditions, turbulent flow is triggered more in the coolant channels. Its characteristic is that the turbulent fluctuations enhance momentum transfer and heat exchange.^[3] Under the same channel size, the convective heat transfer coefficient of turbulence can be 3 to 5 times higher than that of laminar flow, thereby improving the heat dissipation efficiency. However, this also brings higher flow resistance and power consumption of the water pump.

2.1.4 In-channel Flow in Passages

This refers to the closed flow process of the coolant within the sealed flow channels, including the water jacket, the radiator tubes, and the working flow channels of the thermostat. The fluid flow patterns within these channels are typically of two types: fully developed or developing internal flow states, whose flow velocity and temperature distribution will change accordingly along the flow direction, depending on the cross-sectional area of the channels, surface roughness, and degree of curvature.^[2] The geometries of these channels and their characteristics determine the flow resistance and local heat transfer distribution; optimizing the design of the channels can improve the uniformity of local cooling for components such as cylinder liners and reduce the disturbance of the near-wall flow field.

2.1.5 Detailed Explanation of Multi-Branch Processes

The engine cooling system uses a parallel flow design. The main coolant flow is split into multiple branches to cool different components, and then returns to the main circulation. After being pumped, the main flow splits into three primary branches: the cylinder block branch mainly cools the cylinder block surface, the cylinder head branch mainly cools the valves and combustion chamber, and the heater core branch is used for heating the vehicle interior. Ultimately, their flows merge before entering the radiator.^[1] This approach ensures that each component receives a coolant flow rate matched to its thermal load, thereby preventing localized overheating of high-temperature components such as the cylinder head, and reducing unnecessary fluid waste in low-temperature components, thus improving the overall energy efficiency of the system.

2.2 Main governing equation

The fluid flow and heat transfer in the engine cooling system follow the fundamental conservation laws, and its main governing equations are shown below:

2.2.1 Continuity equation (representing conservation of mass):

For the flow of incompressible coolant (commonly applicable under engine operating conditions with small density variations), the general continuity equation is: $\rho \partial t + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0$ (Which simplifies to: $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$)

2.2.2 Momentum equation (Navier-Stokes equation):

Consider viscosity while describing the transfer of fluid momentum: $\rho(\mathbf{u} \partial t + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + \rho \mathbf{g}$ (Where p represents static pressure, μ represents dynamic viscosity, and \mathbf{g} is the acceleration due to gravity.)

2.2.3 Energy equation:

Describes its heat transfer when coupled with fluid motion: $\rho c_p (T \partial t + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T) = k \nabla^2 T + \mu \Phi$ (Where c_p is the specific heat capacity, k is the thermal conductivity, and Φ is the viscous dissipation term.)

2.2.4 Reynolds number:

This is a dimensionless parameter that distinguishes the flow state: $Re = \rho u d / \mu = u d / \nu$ (Where u is the average flow velocity, d is the hydraulic diameter, and ν is the kinematic viscosity.)

2.3 The impact of flow patterns on cooling performance

The flow characteristics of the fluid directly determine the heat transfer efficiency, temperature uniformity and energy consumption of the cooling system. This forced convection circulation provides the most basic power for the cooling circuit, breaking the limitation of low flow velocity in natural convection, which is a necessary condition for the operation of high-load engines. The steady-state - transient flow regulation enables the system to match the dynamic heat load, thereby maintaining the engine operating temperature within the optimal range (85 - 95°C) under different working conditions. Turbulence enhances the intensity of convective heat transfer, which is the core mechanism for achieving efficient heat dissipation in compact cooling channels, although this requires a trade-off with flow resistance. The fluid flow state within the channel determines the local heat transfer distribution, and optimizing the channel design can suppress hot spots on the heat components. Multi-branch diversion enables targeted cooling for different components, enhancing the uniformity of overall cooling and reducing the additional power consumption of the cooling system.

3. Three Advanced Cooling Technologies for Electric Vehicle Batteries

As the electric car (EV) industry is rapidly growing, batteries will be required for increased power output, faster charging times and more consistent performance. But there are major thermal management challenges with fast charging. The heat produced is more apparent when the battery is in a high state of charge. Failure to remove this heat in a timely fashion can lead to diminished charging efficiency, degradation and safety issues including internal short circuit. [5]

Due to their high energy density and performance, lithium-ion batteries are commonly employed in electric vehicles. As a result of the electrochemical reactions within the cells, heat is continually generated during high current charging, particularly at high levels of SoC. Over-temperature will cause higher internal resistance, accelerate capacity loss and reduce long-term performance. Thus, the safety of the batteries and charging efficiency depend on effective cooling technology.

Liquid based cooling technologies have been subject of much attention among the various methods of thermal management. However, the performance of these varies according to the cooling structure, the type of coolant and its application to the cooling situations. In this section, three typical techniques: external liquid cooling, heat pipe cooling and intercell cooling are discussed based on the available literature.

3.1 External Liquid Cooling

External liquid cooling is an integration between the vehicle battery cooling system and charging system. With this method, low temperature cooling, for example with 5 ° C water, with HDPF 50/50 coolant or with RELC NF coolant is brought into the battery pack during charging to cool it off. It is meant to make up for the cooling capacity the vehicle's on-board thermal management system may not have to cool the battery, particularly during ultra-fast charging.

The cooling effect is very much dependent on the configuration of the cooling plates. In the bottom cooling or two-side cooling, the contact area is small, while the three-side cooling structure has a large contact area. In this case, the cooling plates are positioned on both sides and from the bottom of the battery module. In this way the heat can be transferred through three contact surfaces and the heat removal efficiency can be enhanced.

3.2 Heat Pipe Cooling

By embedding flat heat pipes in the liquid cooling system, heat pipe cooling enhances battery thermal management. The principle of its operation is called the principle of phase change, which involves the change of

physical state of a substance without altering its chemical nature.

As the battery produces heat, the working fluid in the heat pipe absorbs the heat and evaporates near the battery. The vapour then flows to the cooler end where it gives up heat and turns back into liquid. The liquid is drawn back into the heated zone by capillary action or gravity and a heat transfer cycle repeats. As a result of this process, flat heat pipes are able to efficiently transfer heat without needing a large amount of external energy.

3.3 Intercell Cooling

Intercell cooling uses heat transfer to cool directly between the battery cells. The coolant flows between the adjacent cells, rather than cooling the outer surface of the module. As a typical design, cooling plates are installed between cells to transfer heat and ethylene propylene rubber sheets are installed to isolate the cells. EPDM sheets prevent cell swelling and provide stability to the structure. A serpentine channel of the cooling plate is used to direct the flow of the coolant in the cooling plate. [7]

The use of a serpentine flow helps to minimize the hotter central portions of the module and eliminates temperature variations between cells. During the passage of the coolant it extracts heat from adjacent cells and decreases the temperature. In contrast to external cooling methods, intercell cooling can achieve better cooling of the inner areas of the battery and can be used to improve the temperature uniformity of the battery.

4. The comparative analysis of cooling technologies is done in the fourth chapter

4.1 External Liquid Cooling

The results of external liquid cooling have demonstrated definite promise in fast charging. After 20 minutes, the maximum and minimum temperatures in the module during 4C charging were 58 ° C and 54.7 ° C, respectively, while they were 50.9 ° C and 43.5 ° C with 3C charging using three-side cooling plates and coolant temperature of 25 ° C.

This approach can also increase the safe charging range. The safe charging range was expanded by 50.1% in 5C charging. In the actual use, the external circulating cooling equipment can be combined with high power charging equipment and can achieve 117km mileage increment with 5C safe charging. [4]

But there are drawbacks to this strategy. It involves co-operation between the vehicle and charging station, and hence a higher cost and more infrastructure. It may also be less stable in extreme environments (caused by environmental temperature) as it may affect its cooling performance.

4.2 Heat Pipe Cooling

Passive heat transfer is the type of heat transfer being used in the flat heat pipe cooling system. It is primarily based on evaporation and condensation, and does not need much additional power. Heat pipes can be used to enhance the longitudinal heat conduction without significantly increasing the structure complexity. [6]

It can be used to decrease the temperature difference within the battery module. Uniformity is important since the quality of performance can be affected and ageing rates increased if temperatures are not uniform. The result indicates that the temperature uniformity of the module can be greatly improved by using 11 flat heat pipes of 128 mm. The upper part of the battery module can be better conductively transferred to the water plate. The maximum temperature difference can be controlled within 5 ° C at a 3C discharge rate. [6]

However, heat pipe cooling may not be adequate for extremely high heat loads. At high power fast charging when the battery SOC is high, battery heat generation could be greater than the heat transfer capacity of the heat pipes. Furthermore, their arrangement and installation need careful design, and may lead to increase of system weight, difficulty and cost in manufacturing and installation.

4.3 Intercell Cooling

Intercell cooling is a powerful approach in high performance battery thermal management since it cools directly between the battery cells. This method is proven to be effective both precooling and preheating. It can heat or cool the battery faster to desired temperatures in both high and low temperature applications with comparatively low

power consumption. [7]

This is particularly critical in fast charging at high states of charge (SoC) where the temperature control directly impacts efficiency and safety. Intercell cooling is able to keep the temperature distribution stable under fast charging. The greater the flow of coolant through the module, the smaller the temperature differential. In one fast charging case, with this method, the maximum battery temperature was reduced to 30.6 ° C, which satisfied and even exceeded the maximum cooling requirement. [7]

The Intercell cooling also contributes to long-term stability in batteries. A more uniform temperature field can help to reduce thermal stress between cells and delay battery aging. It will use more power than passive cooling methods like flat heat pipe cooling, but will be more appropriate for high-SoC fast charging because its performance, safety and lifetime are superior.

5. Conclusion

The three types of cooling, external liquid, heat pipe and intercell cooling, have their own advantages and disadvantages. The external liquid cooling enables external cooling during ultra-fast charging, which can significantly enhance the cooling performance, particularly in combination with high-power charging infrastructure. It does, however, do need extra equipment and can be impacted by ambient conditions.

Passive and efficient heat pipe cooling. Can enhance temperature uniformity and decrease the complexity of structure to a certain level. But it may not have the cooling capacity to effectively deal with the heat generated by the battery during high power fast charge.

Of the three, the intercell cooling provides the best overall performance for the batteries at high SoC. It directly cools the gaps between the cells, and thus enables to get higher temperature uniformity and more stable temperature control. While it is a more energy consuming solution when compared to passive cooling solutions, its advantages of charging efficiency, safety and battery life make it more apt in high-SoC fast charging applications.

As thermodynamics, fluid mechanics and battery system design research further evolves, EV thermal management technologies are expected to be more efficient and integrated in the future. To address the needs for safer, faster and more reliable charging of electric vehicles, more advanced cooling systems might develop.

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